

Transform2Open

Competency Profiles

for the Open Access Transformation

Imprint

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Abstract

The following competency profiles were developed by Transform2Open – a project funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – and serve as a guide for identifying important and relevant open access competencies. They primarily serve as an aid for creating syllabi and curricula for vocational training, degree programs, and continuing education programs for prospective and current academic library staff.

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Introduction¹

Open Access is a broad and diverse field requiring not only traditional but new competencies from library staff. Ideally, staff should develop these during vocational training programs and university study. As the field continues to evolve and remains dynamic, open access also demands current library staff demonstrate a clear commitment to pursuing ongoing training and professional development.

These competency profiles, developed by Transform2Open – a project funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – are intended as a guide for identifying important and relevant open access skills. These competencies represent “the conjunction of knowledge and skill [necessary] to carry out the practical demands [of a job]”² in the area of open access and are intended primarily to serve as an aid for creating syllabi and curricula for vocational training, degree programs, and continuing education programs.³

The authors first drafted the present competency profiles following comprehensive desk research, including a literature and curriculum review, as well as an analysis of job postings with open access duties. Practitioners and educators from vocational training and university library science programs subsequently discussed and commented on the draft competencies in a workshop on May 14, 2024. The feedback was then used to rework the profiles. Structurally, the competencies are divided into five areas and broken out into the three levels of education and training relevant to library staff. In what follows, this is presented in tabular form in two ways: first sorted by area, then by educational level.

In developing these profiles, the authors made several key decisions. Open access is an integral part of the broader open science framework and is therefore given central consideration in the competency profiles. Other competencies that represent independent and complex fields—such as research data management—could not be addressed in the same detail. Likewise, certain competencies relevant to implementation of open access, such as general management expertise, were not included. These skills are indeed important but better understood as basic foundational competencies. By contrast, this publication focuses on specific topics and competencies of particular relevance to the field of open access.

¹ The following document was drafted with a German audience and educational system in mind. Transform2Open nonetheless considers it of general interest and welcomes its adaptation and use in other contexts.

² <https://www.bibb.de/de/8570.php>, translation Transform2Open

³ Although these competency profiles may prove helpful when drafting job descriptions and advertisements, they are primarily meant as a tool for vocational training and educational purposes. The following publication is particularly useful as a resource for creating job descriptions: Berufsverband Information Bibliothek e.V. (Hrsg.): Arbeitsvorgänge in Bibliotheken. 2. Wissenschaftliche Bibliotheken (AVWB) und Staatliche Bücherei- und Bibliotheksfachstellen (AVBF), Berlin 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783111087177>.

Competency Profiles (by area)

Area 1: General

FaMI (Vocational Training)	Bachelor	Master
can describe the general goals and origins of the open access movement	can describe the goals and origins of the open access movement, as well as the relevant declarations (e.g., Berlin Declaration) and situate them in the context of current developments	can describe the goals and origins of the open access movement, as well as the relevant declarations (e.g., Berlin Declaration) and situate them in the context of current developments and critically assess the role of open access in research policy.
can describe the different routes to open access (e.g., Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid) and distinguish between them	can describe the different routes to open access (e.g., Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid), distinguish between them, and explain their respective advantages and disadvantages	can describe the different routes to open access (e.g., Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid), distinguish between them, and explain and critically assess their respective advantages and disadvantages
understands the general role of licenses (especially Creative Commons) in the open access context, as well as the difference between “freely accessible” and “open access”	understands the role of licenses (especially Creative Commons) in the open access context, can differentiate between the different license types and explain the difference between “freely accessible” and “open access”	understands the role of licenses (especially Creative Commons) in the open access context, can differentiate between the different license types and explain their respective advantages and disadvantages, can explain the difference between “freely accessible” and “open access” and assess the implications
–	has basic knowledge of various open access (business) models and agreement types (e.g., diamond open access, institutional publishing, DEAL and other publish-and-read agreements) through which open access can be achieved	has a sound understanding of various open access (business) models and agreement types (e.g., diamond open access, institutional publishing, DEAL and other publish-and-read agreements) through which open access can be achieved and can critically assess their respective advantages and disadvantages as well as the related market dynamics

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Area 2: Research and Policy Environment, including Funding Structures

FaMI (Vocational Training)	Bachelor	Master
<p>can process open access funding applications – for example, for publication or monograph funds – in accordance with the prescribed funding criteria (e.g., DFG funding guidelines or “Quality Standards for Open Access Books”) in a structured workflow</p>	<p>can independently process open access funding applications – for example, for publication or monograph funds – in accordance with the prescribed funding criteria (e.g., DFG funding guidelines or “Quality Standards for Open Access Books”)</p>	<p>is conversant with the relevant open access funding recommendations (e.g., DFG funding guidelines or “Quality Standards for Open Access Books”) as well as the key policy guidelines and recommendations at state, federal, and international levels (e.g., from the DFG, the Alliance of Science Organizations, and Plan S), can develop, establish, and manage appropriate funding instruments (e.g., publication and monograph funds) at the institutional level and, if necessary, secure external funding for them</p>
–	<p>can understand an institutional open access policy and its structure and explain its significance for an institution</p>	<p>can develop an institutional open access strategy, including an open access policy, with relevant stakeholders – taking into consideration state-specific, national, and international contexts, recommendations, and policies – and support its implementation</p>
–	<p>can identify the relevant sections of copyright law for open access (including, where relevant, the right to self-archive) and explain their general significance</p>	<p>can identify the relevant sections of copyright law for open access (including, where relevant, the right to self-archive), explain their significance, and draw on this knowledge when advising</p>

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-	can explain the general significance of established metrics relevant to research evaluation (e.g., impact factor and H-index)	understands the significance of established metrics relevant to research evaluation (e.g., impact factor and H-index) as well as the various policy initiatives aimed at reforming research evaluation systems (e.g., DORA and CoARA) and can explain and assess their relevance for an institution
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Area 3: Advising and Information Literacy Instruction

FaMI (Vocational Training)	Bachelor	Master
can use structured materials to provide researchers with information about an institution's various open access offerings and agreements—including self-archiving services and diamond open access journals—as well as about standard topics and tools in the field of open access (e.g., Creative Commons licenses and “Think. Check. Submit.”)	can advise researchers in routine cases about an institution's various open access offerings and agreements—including self-archiving services and diamond open access journals—as well as about standard topics and tools in the field of open access (e.g., Creative Commons licenses and “Think. Check. Submit.”)	can advise researchers in routine and complex cases about an institution's various open access offerings and agreements—including self-archiving services and diamond open access journals—as well as about standard topics and tools in the field of open access (e.g., Creative Commons licenses and “Think. Check. Submit.”)
–	can prepare and deliver basic instructional content about standard open access topics	can evaluate existing advising services and trainings about open access topics, identify opportunities for improvement, and develop and/or (re)conceptualize formats for providing information

Area 4: Publication and Cost Tracking/Bibliometrics

FaMI (Vocational Training)	Bachelor	Master
can identify the publication and financial metadata underlying open access business processes (e.g., APC, BPC, color charges) and, with guidance, use this to collect data for an information budget or external open access reporting	can identify the publication and financial metadata underlying open access business processes (e.g., APC, BPC, color charges) and use this to independently collect data for an information budget or external open access reporting	based on a sound understanding of the publication and financial metadata underlying open access business processes (e.g., APC, BPC, color charges), can analyze, optimize, automate, or develop new workflows for data capture, for example, for an information budget or external open access reporting
understands the general role of PIDs, can identify the PIDs relevant to open access workflows (e.g., ORCID, DOI), can, with guidance, record, verify, and, if necessary, correct them within existing workflows	understands the role of PIDs, can identify the PIDs relevant to open access workflows (e.g., ORCID, DOI) and can independently record, verify, and, if necessary, correct them within existing workflows	understands the role of PIDs, has advanced knowledge of the PIDs relevant within open access workflows (e.g., ORCID, DOI), can strategically integrate them into institutional workflows and design reporting workflows using them
–	–	can assess publication and cost tracking outputs as well as independent bibliometric analyses, evaluate the added value of existing and new agreements, identify needs for strategic decisions on an institutional level, develop budgetary plans accordingly, and consult with relevant stakeholders where necessary

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Area 5: Infrastructure, including Institutional Publishing

FaMI (Vocational Training)	Bachelor	Master
understands the general role of an institutional repository, can distinguish it from that of a disciplinary repository, and can, with guidance, support established repository workflows (including for self-archiving)	understands the role of an institutional repository, can distinguish it from that of a disciplinary repository, and can independently carry out and supervise established repository workflows (including for self-archiving)	can analyze an institution's established repository services, identify potential for their further development and design new services while clearly distinguishing these from those of disciplinary repositories
can, with guidance, carry out established workflows in tools such as OJS as part of an institutional publishing program	understands the general role of institutional publishing in the open access transformation and can independently carry out existing workflows in tools such as OJS	can critically assess the role of institutional publishing in the open access transformation, evaluate relevant tools and services (e.g., OJS, OMP), assess their relevance for local needs, and support their implementation at the institutional level where relevant

Competency Profiles (by educational level)

FaMI (Vocational Training)

Area	Competency
General	can describe the general goals and origins of the open access movement
	can describe the different routes to open access (e.g., Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid) and distinguish between them
	understands the general role of licenses (especially Creative Commons) in the open access context, as well as the difference between “freely accessible” and “open access”
Research and policy environment, including funding structures	can process open access funding applications – for example, for publication or monograph funds – in accordance with the prescribed funding criteria (e.g., DFG funding guidelines or “Quality Standards for Open Access Books”) in a structured workflow
Advising and Information Literacy Instruction	can use structured materials to provide researchers with information about an institution’s various open access offerings and agreements—including self-archiving services and diamond open access journals—as well as about standard topics and tools in the field of open access (e.g., Creative Commons licenses and “Think. Check. Submit.”)
Publication and Cost Tracking/Bibliometrics	can identify the publication and financial metadata underlying open access business processes (e.g., APC, BPC, color charges) and, with guidance, use this to collect data for an information budget or external open access reporting
	understands the general role of PIDs, can identify the PIDs relevant to open access workflows (e.g., ORCID, DOI), can, with guidance, record, verify, and, if necessary, correct them within existing workflows
Infrastructure, including Institutional Publishing	understands the general role of an institutional repository, can distinguish it from that of a disciplinary repository, and can, with guidance, support established repository workflows (including for self-archiving)
	can, with guidance, carry out established workflows in tools such as OJS as part of an institutional publishing program

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Bachelor

Area	Competency
General	can describe the goals and origins of the open access movement, as well as the relevant declarations (e.g., Berlin Declaration) and situate them in the context of current developments
	can describe the different routes to open access (e.g., Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid), distinguish between them, and explain their respective advantages and disadvantages
	understands the role of licenses (especially Creative Commons) in the open access context, can differentiate between the different license types and explain the difference between “freely accessible” and “open access”
	has basic knowledge of various open access (business) models and agreement types (e.g., diamond open access, institutional publishing, DEAL and other publish-and-read agreements) through which open access can be achieved
Research and Policy Environment, including Funding Structures	can independently process open access funding applications – for example, for publication or monograph funds – in accordance with the prescribed funding criteria (e.g., DFG funding guidelines or “Quality Standards for Open Access Books”)
	can understand an institutional open access policy and its structure and explain its significance for an institution
	can identify the relevant sections of copyright law for open access (including, where relevant, the right to self-archive) and explain their general significance
	can explain the general significance of established metrics relevant to research evaluation (e.g., impact factor and H-index)
Advising and Information Literacy Instruction	can advise researchers in routine cases about an institution’s various open access offerings and agreements—including self-archiving services and diamond open access journals—as well as about standard topics and tools in the field of open access (e.g., Creative Commons licenses and “Think. Check. Submit.”)
	can prepare and deliver basic instructional content about standard open access topics
Publication and Cost Tracking/Bibliometrics	can identify the publication and financial metadata underlying open access business processes (e.g., APC, BPC, color charges) and use this to independently collect data for an information budget or external open access reporting
	understands the role of PIDs, can identify the PIDs relevant to open access workflows (e.g., ORCID, DOI) and can independently record, verify, and, if necessary, correct them within existing workflows

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Infrastructure, including Institutional Publishing

understands the role of an institutional repository, can distinguish it from that of a disciplinary repository, and can independently carry out and supervise established repository workflows (including for self-archiving)

understands the general role of institutional publishing in the open access transformation and can independently carry out existing workflows in tools such as OJS

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Master

Area	Competency
General	can describe the goals and origins of the open access movement, as well as the relevant declarations (e.g., Berlin Declaration) and situate them in the context of current developments and critically assess role of open access in research policy.
	can describe the different routes to open access (e.g., Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid), distinguish between them, and explain and critically assess their respective advantages and disadvantages
	understands the role of licenses (especially Creative Commons) in the open access context, can differentiate between the different license types and explain their respective advantages and disadvantages, can explain the difference between “freely accessible” and “open access” and assess the implications
	has a sound understanding of various open access (business) models and agreement types (e.g., diamond open access, institutional publishing, DEAL and other publish-and-read agreements) through which open access can be achieved and can critically assess their respective advantages and disadvantages as well as the related market dynamics
Research and Policy Environment, including Funding Structures	is conversant with the relevant open access funding recommendations (e.g., DFG funding guidelines or “Quality Standards for Open Access Books”) as well as the key policy guidelines and recommendations at state, federal, and international levels (e.g., from the DFG, the Alliance of Science Organizations, and Plan S), can develop, establish, and manage appropriate funding instruments (e.g., publication and monograph funds) at the institutional level and, if necessary, secure external funding for them
	can develop an institutional open access strategy, including an open access policy, with relevant stakeholders – taking into consideration state-specific, national, and international contexts, recommendations, and policies – and support its implementation
	can identify the relevant sections of copyright law for open access (including, where relevant, the right to self-archive), explain their significance, and draw on this knowledge when advising
	understands the significance of established metrics relevant to research evaluation (e.g., impact factor and H-index) as well as the various policy initiatives aimed at reforming research evaluation systems (e.g., DORA and CoARA) and can explain and assess their relevance for an institution

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Advising and Information Literacy Instruction	can advise researchers in routine and complex cases about an institution's various open access offerings and agreements—including self-archiving services and diamond open access journals—as well as about standard topics and tools in the field of open access (e.g., Creative Commons licenses and “Think. Check. Submit.”)
	can evaluate existing advising services and trainings about open access topics, identify opportunities for improvement, and develop and/or (re)conceptualize formats for providing information
Publication and Cost Tracking/Bibliometrics	based on a sound understanding of the publication and financial metadata underlying open access business processes (e.g., APC, BPC, color charges), can analyze, optimize, automate, or develop new workflows for data capture, for example, for an information budget or external open access reporting
	understands the role of PIDs, has advanced knowledge of the PIDs relevant within open access workflows (e.g., ORCID, DOI), can strategically integrate them into institutional workflows and design reporting workflows using them
	can assess publication and cost tracking outputs as well as independent bibliometric analyses, evaluate the added value of existing and new agreements, identify needs for strategic decisions on an institutional level, develop budgetary plans accordingly, and consult with relevant stakeholders where necessary
Infrastructure, including Institutional Publishing	can analyze an institution's established repository services, identify potential for their further development and design new services while clearly distinguishing these from those of disciplinary repositories
	can critically assess the role of institutional publishing in the open access transformation, evaluate relevant tools and services (e.g., OJS, OMP), assess their relevance for local needs, and support their implementation at the institutional level where relevant
